

EIJASTR

EUROPEAN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF APPLIED SCIENCES AND THEORETICAL RESEARCH

International Scientific Journal

2026

European International Journal Of Applied Sciences And Theoretical Research

Volume 02, Issue 05

EDITORIAL BOARD:**Professor Emma Franke**

Editor in Chief

Prof. Jo Coldwell-Neilson

Associate Editor In Chief Deakin University, Australia

Mr Mohd Helmy

Abd Wahab Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia

Shafi'i Muhammad Abdulhamid

Federal University Of Technology Minna, Nigeria., Nigeria

Dr Man Fung (Kelvin) Lo

The Chinese University Of Hong Kong, Hong Kong

Dr Ahmad Samed

Al-Adwan Al Ahliyya Amman University, Jordan

Waleed Alsabhan

Kacst, Saudi Arabia Yvonne Antonucci Widener University, United States

Prof. Orit Avidov Ungar

Achva Academic College & Open University Of Israel, Israel

Dr. Aslina Baharum

Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Malaysia

ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE AND WAYS OF EFFECTIVE USE OF CAPITAL IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

Mukhtarov Makhmudjon Marifovich

Andijan state technical institute

Department of " Economics " associate professor

E-mail: m.m.muxtorov@mail.ru

Abstract. This article analyzes the economic importance of the effective use of capital funds in industrial enterprises, its impact on production efficiency, and ways to improve the management of capital resources. It also highlights the possibilities of increasing economic efficiency through the rational use of fixed and working capital, the correct organization of investment policy, and the modernization of enterprise activities.

Keywords: capital funds, industrial enterprises, economic efficiency, fixed assets, working capital, investment, modernization, resource utilization, production, financial management.

The industrial sector is the main pillar of the country's economic potential, and its effective operation largely depends on the level of rational use of capital funds. Therefore, the effective use of capital funds in industrial enterprises is considered the main factor ensuring production efficiency. Capital funds serve to form the fixed and circulating assets of the enterprise, organize the production process and modernize it. Their correct distribution and effective use make it possible to reduce the cost of production, increase labor productivity and ensure the overall profitability of the enterprise. On the contrary, the ineffective use of capital funds leads to excessive costs in the production process, waste of resources and a decrease in the financial stability of the enterprise.

Today, increased competition in the economy, deepening market relations, and the rapid introduction of innovative technologies require enterprises to effectively manage capital. In particular, it is important to properly direct investments, use modern equipment, and introduce resource-

saving technologies in the processes of modernization and technological renewal.

The issue of effective use of capital funds in industrial enterprises has been widely studied in economic sciences, and a number of scientific studies have been conducted in this direction by domestic and foreign scientists. In the literature, capital funds, their composition, performance indicators, and investment management issues have been analyzed based on different approaches. In particular, VM Serov, Yu.P. Tikhonov in their studies paid special attention to the study of the economic results of industrial enterprises, the difference in the efficiency of the enterprise in which the investment was made, the efficiency of manufacturers of the same type of product, the introduction of preferential investments in a specific sector, and the improvement of production technologies¹, while YN Simionova also assessed the economic efficiency of industrial enterprises in terms of changes in capital investments, the results of the implementation of investment projects, and the impact of changes in the value and market value of newly established production capacities on economic results. In the studies, the impact of investments and capital investments in industrial enterprises on economic efficiency was analyzed based on different approaches². The first approach focuses on the difference in efficiency between enterprises with and without investment, the efficiency of enterprises producing the same product, and the impact of technological improvements. In this case, the role of investment in increasing production efficiency is revealed through a comparative method. In the second approach, economic efficiency is systematically assessed through changes in the volume of capital investments, the results of investment projects, the formation of new production capacities, and changes in their market value. This approach is distinguished by the fact that it covers the impact of capital not only on production, but also on market prices. Today, along with the above, the main issue is the internal management and optimal

1. В.М.Серов, Ю.П. Тихинов “Сравнительной оценке экономической эффективности инвестиционных вложений в производственный капитал” Вестник университета № 5, 2023 ст.131-141.

2. Симионова Н.Е. Инвестиционные проекты в строительстве: управление и оценка эффективности. Экономика строительства. 2020;2 (62):59–65 с

allocation mechanisms of capital funds, as well as a full assessment of the long-term economic effectiveness of investments.

In their research, V.B. Daskovskiy and V.B. Kiselev determined the most acceptable indicator of internal rate of return on investments for comparative assessment of the economic efficiency of investment projects from the following equation.

$$\sum_{t=0}^N (B_t - Z_t) \frac{1}{(1+Ye)_t} = \sum_{t=0}^N I_t \frac{1}{(1+Ye)_t} \quad (1)$$

In economic terms, the value of E represents the traditional coefficient of economic efficiency of capital investments, equal to the ratio of the amount of profit as an economic result of the implementation of an investment project to the amount of capital investments made³. In practice, the efficiency of the use of capital investments in industrial enterprises can be determined based on the following indicators (Table 1):

Table 1

Classification of indicators of efficiency of capital investment use⁴

Indicator	Description
Capital capacity	The amount of output per 1 soum of capital investment
Return on capital	Product created / Capital investment
Return on capital	Return on investment / Investment amount
Capital turnover period	Capital investment / Annual profit (in how many years will it be paid off)
Capital investment per worker	Capital / Number of employees
Capital-intensity	Ratio of capital investment to gross domestic product
Production efficiency index	Product volume / Resource volume (based on multi-factor indices)

Each of the indicators presented reflects how efficiently capital resources are used in the production process. Capital efficiency and return on capital indicate the relationship between output and capital. Return on capital allows

3. ³ Дасковский В.Б., Киселев В.Б. Новый подход к экономическому обоснованию инвестиций. М.: Канон РООИ «Реабилитация»; 2016. 400 с

⁴ Author's development as a result of research

us to assess the level of profit received from investments. The capital turnover period reflects the rate of return on capital investments.

To assess the development of the industrial sector, modernization of production and the development of high-tech industries in the national economy, it is necessary to assess the capital capacity indicator. The capital capacity indicator is considered the main criterion for determining investment activity, the level of resource utilization and production efficiency. Table 1 below reflects the trend of changes in capital capacity in the general economy and industrial sectors in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Andijan region for 2015-2025.

Table 4.1.4

**Dynamics of capital capacity index for the Republic of Uzbekistan and
Andijan region⁵**

Indicators	2015.	2017.	2021.	2022.	2023.	2024.	2024.
Capital capacity (country 's economy) according to)	0.26	0.24	0.29	0.28	0.30	0.34	0.32
Capital capacity (Andijan region economy according to)	0.14	0.13	0.23	0.23	0.24	0.31	0.3
Capital intensity (by country 's industry)	0.45	0.49	0.47	0.48	0.59	0.6 5	0.58
Capital capacity (by industry sector in Andijan region)	0.04	0.06	0.14	0.13	0.15	0.16	0.16
Capital capacity (Andijan region textile industry) by industry sector)	0.36	0.36	0.22	0.26	0.20	0.30	0.27

According to the results of the study, the capital capacity coefficient in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan was 0.26 in 2015, and by 2024 it was formed in the range of 0.32–0.34. This dynamics indicates an increase in investment activity in the country's economy, an expansion of the volume of investments directed to fixed capital, and an increase in the importance of the capital factor in economic growth processes. In the economy of Andijan region, the capital capacity coefficient was 0.14 in 2015, and reached 0.30–0.31 in 2024.

⁵Calculations based on data from the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Andijan Regional Statistics Department .

This situation can be explained by a significant increase in capital investments in the economy of the region, an expansion of production potential, and industrialization processes. The capital capacity coefficient for the country's industrial sector was 0.45 in 2015 and was formed in the range of 0.58–0.65 by 2024, while the capital capacity coefficient in the industry of Andijan region increased from 0.04 to 0.16. Although the region started from a low base, the investment climate in the industrial sector improved and industrial development processes gradually intensified. The capital capacity coefficient in the textile industry of Andijan region was 0.36 in 2015, decreased to 0.22 in 2021, and then in the range of 0.27–0.30 in 2024. Thus, an upward trend in the capital capacity coefficient is observed at all considered levels. This indicates an increase in investment activity in the economy, an increase in the volume of capital investments, and an increasing role of the capital factor in production processes. The fluctuating dynamics observed in the textile industry indicate that the sector is sensitive to technological innovations, production efficiency, and market conditions.

Therefore, for the effective use of capital funds in industrial enterprises, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- further improving investment policy in order to optimize the capital capacity of the economy, in particular, prioritizing capital attraction to sectors that create high added value;
- Increasing the level of efficient use of capital by modernizing production in the industrial sector of Andijan region, introducing modern technologies, and renewing fixed assets;
- Introduction of innovative technologies, automated production systems, and resource-saving methods to increase the efficiency of capital investments in the textile industry;
- It is necessary to stabilize capital flows by improving the regional investment climate, expanding private sector participation, and developing public-private partnership mechanisms.

References

1. В.М.Серов, Ю.П. Тихинов “Сравнительной оценке экономической эффективности инвестиционных вложений в производственный капитал” Вестник университета № 5, 2023 ст.131-141.
2. Симионова Н.Е. Инвестиционные проекты в строительстве: управление и оценка эффективности. Экономика строительства. 2020;2 (62):59–65 с

3. Xamdamov, R. “То‘qimachilik sanoatining global iqtisodiyotdagi o‘rni va samaradorligi. Global iqtisodiyot va raqobatbardoshlik. 2021-yil 18(2), 101-107.
4. Дасковский В.Б., Киселев В.Б. Новый подход к экономическому обоснованию инвестиций. М.: Канон РООИ «Реабилитация»; 2016. 400 с
5. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Milliy statistika qo‘mitasi va Andijon viloyati statistika boshqarmasi ma’lumotlari asosida muallif hisob-kitobi.
6. Marifovich, M. M. (2023). The effect of product diversification on the economic efficiency of industrial enterprises. *Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (68).
7. Mukhtarov, M. (2023). Ways to increase the economic efficiency of textile industry.